

Some Faunistic Records of Heteroptera (Hemiptera) in Mardin (Turkey) with an Endemic Species

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ABSTRACT: We represents *Apterola lownii* (Saunders, 1876) and *Grypocoris melanopygus* Horváth, 1906 two species, found in Mardin, less known in photographic images. *Grypocoris melanopygus* Horváth, 1906 endemic to Turkey, shows a new color pattern.

KEYWORDS: : *Apterola lownii*, *Grypocoris melanopygus*, Mardin province, Eastern Turkey, faunistic records.

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INTRODUCTION

In this paper we present the reports of two species of Heteroptera generally less known by photographic images in nature. They are present in the province of Mardin where historically *Apterola lownii* (Saunders, 1876) was found the first time. Therefore is presented the red-orange pattern of *Grypocoris melanopygus* Horváth, 1906, usually white-yellow colored. General distribution, when not otherwise specified, is referred to the

Catalogue of Palaearctic Region (Aukema & Rieger 1999 and 2001; Aukema et al., 2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lygaeidae

Apterola lownii (Saunders, 1876)

General distribution: Europe: Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia, Turkey (European part). Asia: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Cyprus, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Kazakhstan (Asian part), Kirgizia, Syria, Tadjikistan, Turkey (Asian

part), Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Distribution in Turkey: Ankara, Edirne, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Mardin, (Önder et al., 2006; Kıyak, 2017)

Material examined: Mardin, 28.03.2019, 5 ex. leg. Geçit.

Remarks: In the present case were found brachypterous specimens.

According to Pericart (1990), the species was generally collected on dry soil under

the stones or between the roots of the trees.

Host plants: in different situations, specimens were found under *Anchusa aggregata* (Cyprus) and *Artemisa herba-alba* (Israel). In Azeirbajjan it was found at the considerable height of 2100 m.

Bio-ecological studies have ascertained the presence of only one generation per year: young instars grow during the

Figure 1. The habitus of *Apterola lownii* (Saunders, 1876). (Photos by İ., Özgen)

Miridae

Grypocoris melanopygus Horváth, 1906

General distribution: This species is endemic in Turkey.

Distribution in Turkey: Ankara, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Tunceli, Pertek, Akdemir (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent., 2017; Özgen & Dioli, 2019).

Material examined: Mardin, 10.05.2019, 2 exc. leg. M. Geçit.

Remarks: The specimen is a mature female having the abdomen full of eggs: for this reason, we can exclude that it is

an immature, with criptic coloration, just passed from the instar of nymph to the adult. In fact, the nominal form usually shows a yellow and black color. In the case of the image reproduced here (Fig. 2), the white-yellow color turns into pink-orange. So we say for the new color form, this color difference can be considered as color variation.

In literature, the species was observed “occurring on undergrowth below *Pinus nigra* of wooded hill formation” (Hoberlandt, 1955). Wagner (1970-71) instead reported an observation by Seidenstücker who found it on *Chrysanthemum* sp.

Figure 2. The habitus of *Grypocoris melanopygus* Horváth, 1906.

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